

Schiff bases of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with phenylenediamines and their metal complexes

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Manuscript received 11 June 2008, revised 31 December 2008, accepted 2 January 2009

Abstract : Reaction of phenylenediamines with 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione yielded a new series of polydentate Schiff base ligands. Spectral and analytical data revealed the condensation of *o*- and *m*-phenylenediamines in the 2 : 1 ratio and *p*-phenylenediamine in the 1 : 2 ratio. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data suggest neutral tetradentate N₄ coordination for the Schiff bases of *o*- and *m*-phenylenediamines with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. In the metal complexes of the Schiff base of *p*-phenylenediamine, the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone protons are replaced by the metal ions.

Keywords : 3-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione, Schiff base, phenylenediamine, IR spectra, ¹H NMR spectra, mass spectra.

Introduction

The Schiff base condensation between a dicarbonyl compound and a di- (or poly-) amine has formed the basis of many successful macrocyclic ligand synthesis¹. These materials could be applied in different areas such as electrochemistry, bioinorganic chemistry, catalysis, metallic deactivators, separation processes and environmental chemistry^{2,3}. Schiff bases of phenylenediamines and their metal complexes have a variety of applications including biological⁴, clinical⁵ and analytical⁶ fields. Although the coordination compounds of Schiff bases of 1,3-diketones have been extensively studied⁷, reports are scanty on Schiff bases derived from arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones. In continuation of our studies on arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones⁸⁻¹³ we report herein the synthesis and characterization of a new series of Schiff bases produced from 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with phenylenediamines. Typical metal complexes of these compounds were also synthesized and characterized.

Results and discussion

Analytical (Table 1) and spectral data of the reaction products of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with phenylenediamines suggest that the condensation has occurred in the 1 : 2 ratio except with *p*-phenylenediamine

where a 2 : 1 condensation product is formed. The compounds are crystalline in nature and are soluble in common organic solvents. They formed well defined and crystalline complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The analytical data (Table 1) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF (specific conductance < 10 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) suggest [M(HL)(OAc)₂] stoichiometry for the complexes of Htop and Htmp. Analytical and spectral data are in agreement with [M₂L₂] stoichiometry for the metal chelates of H₂tp. The Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The Ni^{II} complexes of Htop and Htmp are paramagnetic and H₂tp is diamagnetic. The observed IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of Htop and Htmp are in conformity with structures 1 and 2 and their metal complexes with structures 3 and 4. Analytical and spectral data of H₂tp are in agreement with structure 5 and its complexes with structure 6. These data of the compounds are discussed separately.

Characterization of Htop, Htmp and their metal complexes :

Infrared spectra : That both the carbonyl groups of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione are involved in the Schiff's base condensation with *o*- and *m*-phenylenedi-

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of Htop, Htmp, H₂tp and their metal complexes

Compd./ Empirical formula	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%):			
			Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
Htop	65	125	61.24 (61.38)	5.34 (5.37)	25.14 (25.06)	-
C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₇ S						
Htmp	70	178	61.30 (61.38)	5.38 (5.37)	25.00 (25.06)	-
C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₇ S						
H ₂ tp	70	180	53.74 (53.65)	3.95 (4.06)	22.74 (22.76)	-
C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ S ₂ O ₂						
[Ni(Htop)(OAc) ₂]	80	296	50.74 (50.73)	4.62 (4.75)	17.34 (17.26)	10.39 (10.33)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ NiSO ₄						
[Cu(Htop)(OAc) ₂]	78	284	50.37 (50.30)	4.76 (4.71)	17.02 (17.11)	10.96 (11.09)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ CuN ₇ SO ₄						
[Zn(Htop)(OAc) ₂]	76	220	50.25 (50.13)	4.64 (4.70)	16.94 (17.06)	11.44 (11.38)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ SO ₄ Zn						
[Ni(Htmp)(OAc) ₂]	75	286	50.84 (50.73)	4.74 (4.75)	17.18 (17.26)	16.21 (16.33)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ NiSO ₄						
[Cu(Htmp)(OAc) ₂]	75	278	50.18 (50.30)	4.78 (4.71)	17.16 (17.11)	10.98 (11.09)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ CuN ₇ SO ₄						
[Zn(Htmp)(OAc) ₂]	70	242	49.98 (50.13)	4.72 (4.70)	17.00 (17.06)	11.30 (11.38)
C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ SO ₄ Zn						
[Ni ₂ (tp) ₂]	60	298	47.75 (47.85)	3.80 (3.81)	20.38 (20.30)	10.60 (10.64)
C ₄₄ H ₄₂ N ₁₆ Ni ₂ S ₄ O ₄						
[Cu ₂ (tp) ₂]	65	284	47.50 (47.44)	3.68 (3.77)	20.08 (20.12)	11.48 (11.42)
C ₄₄ H ₄₂ Cu ₂ N ₁₆ S ₄ O ₄						
[Zn ₂ (tp) ₂]	65	234	47.38 (47.28)	3.66 (3.76)	19.98 (20.06)	11.74 (11.71)
C ₄₄ H ₄₂ N ₁₆ S ₄ O ₄ Zn ₂						

-OAc - Acetate

amines is clearly indicated in the IR spectra of Htop and Htmp. Thus the spectra of the compounds in the region 1600–1800 cm⁻¹ showed no band assignable to free acetyl carbonyl. However the spectra displayed three medium intensity bands at ~1630, 1620 and 1610 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively to the stretching of the hydrazone, imine and thiazole C=N groups¹⁴. Several medium intensity bands observed in the 1550–1600 cm⁻¹ region are due to C=C functions. Several weak but prominent absorptions in the 2500–3000 cm⁻¹ region of the spectra are due to various νC–H vibrations. The presence of several medium intensity bands in the range 1500–1550 cm⁻¹ is due to in-plane bending vibration of NH groups. In the IR spectra of the metal complexes of Htop and Htmp, the strong band at ~1620 cm⁻¹ of the free ligand due to νC=N (imine) shifted to a low wave number and appeared as a prominent band at ~1560 cm⁻¹. The hydrazone and thiazole νC=N are only marginally affected in the spectra of all the com-

plexes. The bending mode of hydrazone NH remained almost unaffected in the spectra of complexes¹⁵. These indicate that the imine nitrogens are involved in bonding with the metal ion while hydrazone and thiazole νC=N are excluded from coordination as in structures 3 and 4. Monodentate acetate usually shows two bands at ~1630 and ~1310 cm⁻¹ due to antisymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively¹⁶. Since hydrazone C=N absorption of the compounds also appeared in this region, the band at ~1630 cm⁻¹ could not be located. However a medium intensity band observed at ~1320 cm⁻¹ suggests the monodentate coordination of the acetate groups. The imino nitrogens and the acetate oxygen are involved in complexation with the metal ion, which is clearly evident from the appearance of new medium intensity bands at ~430 cm⁻¹ and ~530 cm⁻¹ assignable to νM–O and νM–N in the spectra¹⁶. Important bands that appeared in the spectra are given in Table 2.

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of Htop, Htmp, H_2tpp and their Zn^{II} complexes

Compd.	NH	NH_2	CH_3	CH_3 of acetate
Htop	9.02 (1H)	4.60 (4H)	2.62 (3H) 2.56 (3H)	-
$[\text{Zn}(\text{top})(\text{OAc})_2]$	9.04 (1H)	5.03 (4H)	2.70 (3H) 2.66 (3H)	2.13 (6H)
Htmp	9.29 (1H)	4.72 (4H)	2.64 (3H) 2.54 (3H)	-
$[\text{Zn}(\text{tmp})(\text{OAc})_2]$	9.33 (1H)	5.13 (4H)	2.69 (3H) 2.64 (3H)	2.11 (6H)
H_2tpp	14.82 (2H)	-	2.63 (6H) 2.52 (6H)	-
$[\text{Zn}_2(\text{tpp})_2]$	-	-	2.65 (12H) 2.50 (12H)	-

Table 4. Mass spectral data of Htop, Htmp, H_2tpp and their Cu^{II} complexes

Compd.	Mass spectral data (m/z)
Htop	391, 376, 361, 307, 298, 278, 205, 113, 93, 84, 77
Htmp	391, 376, 361, 307, 298, 278, 205, 113, 93, 84, 77
H_2tpp	495, 479, 451, 435, 410, 393, 381, 326, 268, 113, 84
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Htop})(\text{OAc})_2]$	574, 572, 461, 459, 515, 513, 456, 454, 439, 426, 424, 391, 376, 331, 278, 205, 93, 84, 77
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Htmp})(\text{OAc})_2]$	574, 572, 461, 459, 515, 513, 456, 454, 439, 426, 424, 391, 376, 331, 298, 278, 113, 93, 84
$[\text{Cu}_2(\text{tpp})_2]$	1115, 1028, 944, 860, 776, 761, 746, 731, 716, 495, 479, 451, 435, 410, 393, 381, 326, 268

formulation. Peaks due to the elimination of CH_3 , $\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{NS}$, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{N}_3\text{S}$ etc. are also observed in the spectra^{9,18}. The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks corresponding to $[\text{CuHL}(\text{OAc})_2]$ stoichiometry. Peaks correspond to L^+ and fragments of L^+ are also present in the spectra. The spectra of the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu isotopes (Table 4).

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the compounds show two broad bands with maxima at ~ 380 nm and ~ 250 nm due to various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complexes (μ_{eff} , ~ 1.70 B.M.) show a broad band centered at ~ 11000 cm^{-1} indicating their octahedral structure¹⁹. The Ni^{II} chelates are paramagnetic (μ_{eff} value ~ 2.80 B.M.) and show three well-separated absorption bands in the spectra at λ_{max} ~ 8150 , ~ 13350 and ~ 24450 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions; $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$; $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. These indicate the existence of the metal ions in a square planar environment with four nitrogens of the Schiff base, and the two acetate groups

occupy *trans* positions of an overall octahedral structure.

Characterization of H_2tpp and its metal complexes :

Infrared spectra : The IR spectrum of H_2tpp showed a strong band at 1655 cm^{-1} due to the stretching of acetyl carbonyl involved in strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding^{9,17,20}. The spectrum of the compound in the 1600 – 1650 cm^{-1} region also displayed three medium intensity bands at 1630 , 1615 and 1608 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ of hydrazone, imine and thiazole groups respectively⁸. The spectrum showed a broad band in the range 2500 – 3500 cm^{-1} due to the existence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the compound as in structure 5. The band due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl of the free ligand disappeared in the spectra of all the metal complexes and instead a new band appeared at ~ 1560 cm^{-1} assignable to metal bonded carbonyl function¹⁶. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibrations of the ligand remained almost unaffected in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating their non-involvement in coordination with the metal ion. The replacement of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone hydrogens by metal ion in all the complexes is clearly indicated from the disappearance of the broad band of the free ligand in the 2500 –

3500 cm^{-1} region of the spectra. Instead several medium intensity bands assignable to various aliphatic and aromatic $\nu\text{C-H}$ vibrations appeared in this region. Spectra of all the complexes show additional medium intensity bands in the 420–450 cm^{-1} and 520–550 cm^{-1} region presumably due to $\nu\text{M-O}$ and $\nu\text{M-N}$ vibrations¹⁶. Important bands that appeared in the spectra are given in Table 2.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectrum of H₂tp displayed a low field two-proton signal at δ 14.82 ppm due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone protons of structure 5. Absence of any signal due to methine proton also supports the hydrazone form of the compound⁸. The phenyl and thiazolyl protons appeared as a complex multiplet in the δ 6.90–7.90 ppm region. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the diamagnetic Zn^{II} complex, the low field signal due to the chelated hydrogen disappeared indicating the replacement of the hydrazone protons by metal ion during complexation¹¹. Integrated intensities of all other protons agree well with the structure 6 of the complexes. The assignments of various proton signals observed are assembled in Table 3.

Mass spectra : The formation of the compound is well confirmed from the presence of an intense P⁺ peak at m/z 495 in its mass spectrum. Fragments correspond to the elimination of CH₃CO, C₃H₂NS, C₃H₃N₂S, C₃H₃N₃S etc. from the parent ion are appeared in the spectrum. The mass spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex clearly shows the presence of a molecular ion peak corresponding to M₂L₂ stoichiometry. Other important peaks appeared in the spec-

trum are due to the elimination of thiazole, Tz-NH, etc. from the molecular ion (Table 4).

Electronic spectra : The UV spectrum of the compound show two broad bands with maxima at 370 nm and 245 nm due to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complex showed a broad visible band, λ_{max} at 15200 cm^{-1} . This, together with the measured μ_{eff} value (1.74 B.M.) suggests the square-planar geometry¹⁹. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at 17600 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the Ni^{II} chelate suggest its square-planar geometry.

ESR spectra : The g_{av} values of the Cu^{II} complexes of Htop, Htmp and H₂ttp are 2.098, 2.090 and 2.080. The values indicate that the complex of H₂ttp has greater covalent character due to extensive delocalization possible compared to other complexes²¹. The spectrum showed four peaks due to coupling of the electron spin with the spin of ⁶³Cu nucleus ($I = 3/2$). The peaks are broad and have the appearance of ill-resolved multiplets due to hyperfine splitting of the coordinated nitrogens of the ligand.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by microanalyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in methanol solution (10^{-4} M) on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr discs) on an 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer, ESR spectra (X-band) at 77 K using a Varian E 112 ESR spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at 28 ± 1 °C using solution of about 10^{-3} M concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of Htop, Htmp and H₂ttp : 3-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione was prepared as reported⁹. An ethanolic solution of phenylenediamine (1.08 g, 0.01 mol, 20 mL) was added to an ethanolic solution of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione (2.11 g, 0.01 mol, 20 mL). The mixture was refluxed for ~3 h on a water bath. The volume was reduced to half and the solution poured into crushed ice with vigorous stirring. The crystalline pro-

duct formed was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from hot methanol twice to get chromatographically (TLC) pure compound.

Synthesis of metal complexes : A concentrated aqueous solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol, 15 mL) was added to a methanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol, 20 mL) and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. The precipitate formed on cooling was filtered, washed with excess water, recrystallized from hot methanol and dried in vacuum.

Conclusion :

Three new Schiff base ligands have been prepared by the condensation of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with phenylenediamines. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data revealed a 1 : 2 product (Htop and Htmp) with 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione and *o*-/*m*-phenylenediamines in which both the carbonyl groups of the dione are involved in Schiff base formation. The condensation of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione and *p*-phenylenediamine yielded a 2 : 1 product. Analytical and spectral data revealed neutral tetradentate N₄ coordination for the Schiff bases of *o*- and *m*-phenylenediamines using the imino and amino nitrogens along with acetate coordination in their Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. The Schiff base of *p*-phenylenediamine behave as dibasic tetradentate ligand in which both the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone protons are replaced by the metal ions.

References

1. W. P. Nawrocka, B. Sztuba, A. Drys, J. Wietrzyk, J. Kosendiak and A. Opolski, *Polish J. Chem.*, 2006, **80**, 279; N. Sandeep, S. J. Bidya, S. S. Chauhan and Y. C. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 441; E. M. Opozda, W. Asocha and B. Wodarczyk-Gajda, *J. Mol. Str.*, 2003, **657**, 199; D. Kumar, A. Syamal and A. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 280.
2. F. Bedioui, G. Gutierrez and C. B. Charreton, "Review of Selected Significant Designs and Applications to the Electrochemical Detection of Pollutants", Paris, 1999.
3. C. S. Salazar and M. I. Toral, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **49**, 169; M. S. Masoud, G. B. Mohamed, Y. H. Abdul-Razek, A. E. Ali and F. N. Khairy, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **46**, 99; A. Campos, J. R. Anaconda and M. M. Campos, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1999, **22**, 283; S. Trevin, F. Bedioui, M. G. Gómez and C. B. Charreton, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 1997, **7**, 923.
4. A. M. Mahindra and J. M. Fischer, *Nature*, 1983, **303**, 64.
5. P. R. Patel, B. T. Thaker and S. Zele, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 563.
6. B. Chiswell and K. W. Lee, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 2315; L. F. Lindoy and S. E. Livingstone, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1149.
7. P. D. Benny, J. L. Green, H. P. Engelbrecht, C. L. Barnes and S. S. Jurisson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 2381; T. D. Thangadurai and K. Natarajan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 549; N. Raman, Y. Pichaikaniraja and A. Kulandaisami, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2001, **113**, 183; B. S. Sankhla, S. Mathur and M. Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1985, **15**, 1121; B. B. Mahapatra and D. Panda, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 117.
8. K. Krishnankutty, P. Sayudevi and Muhammed Basheer Ummathur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 48; 2007, **84**, 518, 337; *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **72**, 1075.
9. K. Krishnankutty and D. K. Babu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 379.
10. K. Krishnankutty and V. T. Rema, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 243.
11. K. Krishnankutty and John Michael, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 238; *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1993, **24**, 259; 1991, **22**, 327.
12. K. Krishnankutty and P. Ummer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 194; 1988, **65**, 213.
13. N. Thankarajan and K. Krishnankutty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 401.
14. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman and Hall, London, 1980.
15. P. Viswanathamurthi, A. Geetha, R. Karvembu and K. Natarajan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 90.
16. N. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1997.
17. D. C. Nonhebel and A. Mitchell, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, **35**, 2013.
18. H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, "Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds", Holden Day, San Francisco, 1967.
19. K. C. Joshi and V. N. Pathak, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **22**, 37.
20. S. A. Sadeek, *J. Argent. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **93**, 165.
21. D. Kivelson and R. Niema, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149; J. R. Wasson and C. Trapp, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 3763.